

HOUSEHOLDS' WILLINGNESS TO PAY FOR IMPROVED PUBLIC WATER SUPPLY IN NIGERIA: EVIDENCE FROM KATSINA STATE

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ABSTRACT

Access to reliable and safe public water supply remains limited across semi-urban communities in Northern Nigeria, raising concerns about service sustainability and cost recovery. This study estimates households' willingness to pay (WTP) for improved public water supply in five semi-urban towns in Katsina State and identifies its socioeconomic determinants. Using primary survey data from 400 households and a Tobit regression model to account for censored responses, we estimate a mean monthly WTP of ₦6,567.88 (US\$4.10), approximately 62% higher than the prevailing tariff. Further result show that, 47% of the households lack access to any public water source with as much as 59% depending on private water vendors to meet their daily water demand. Additionally, household income, age, education, cost of alternative water sources and water quality was the key drivers for WTP. These findings reveal substantial latent demand for improved public water services and suggest scope for tariff reform to enhance financial sustainability, provided that affordability safeguards are implemented. Moreover, the results contribute new evidence from a semi-urban Northern Nigerian context, informing on-going infrastructure expansion and cost-recovery strategies.

Keywords: Improved public water supply, willingness to pay (WTP), Nigeria

JEL Codes: D12, Q25, Q5

1. INTRODUCTION

Access to adequate and safe drinking water has long been recognised as a fundamental determinant of socio-economic development. The Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 6, Target 6.1, seeks to “achieve universal and equitable access to safe and affordable drinking water for all by 2030” (United Nations [UN], 2015). A growing body of empirical evidence has links access to safe drinking water to improve public health outcomes, enhanced productivity, economic growth, food security, better nutrition, increased school attendance and reductions in poverty and water-borne diseases (Abanyie et al., 2023; Akumiah, 2007; Gallandat et al., 2021; Graveleau et al., 2021; Lowe et al., 2019; Moriarty & Butterworth, 2003; WHO, 2004, 2011).

Over the past two decades, approximately two billion people worldwide have gained access to safely managed drinking water services (WHO, UNICEF, World Bank, 2022). Despite this progress, substantial access gaps persist. An estimated 400 million people in sub-Saharan Africa and about 110 million Nigerians still lack access to safe drinking water services (The

Corporate Accountability and Public Participation Africa [CAPPA], 2024; WHO, UNICEF, World Bank, 2022). In Nigeria, regional disparities remain pronounced. The Federal Ministry of Water Resources (FMWR, 2022) estimates that 56% (26.5 million) of residents in the North-West and 45% (5 million) of residents in Katsina State lack access to at least basic water supply services. These deficits pose significant threats to population health and welfare. Globally, it is estimated that nearly 1.4 million deaths in 2019 alone could have been prevented through universal access to water and sanitation services (WHO, 2023).

Despite sustained efforts by governments, donor agencies, and non-governmental organisations (NGOs), improvements in access to safe water services remain constrained by rapid population growth, climate change, and inadequate financing for infrastructure investment, operations, and maintenance (Ahmed et al., 2022; Abdullahi, & Kwarah, 2025; Nadabo, et al., 2024; Abdurraheem, et al., 2025; Olayemi, et al., 2021; Tenaw, & Assfaw, 2022). Consequently, assessing households' willingness to pay (WTP) for improved water services has attracted considerable scholarly attention worldwide (Dutta et al., 2005; Entele & Lee, 2019; Eridadi et al., 2021; Getinet et al., 2024; Islam et al., 2022; Jianjun et al., 2016; Kebede & Tariku, 2016; Odwori, 2020; Rahman et al., 2017; Zvobgo, 2021), as well as in Nigeria, particularly in the Southern region (Adenike & Titus, 2009; Akeju et al., 2018; Coster & Otufale, 2014, 2016; Dare, 2014; Itoro, 2024; Kanayo et al., 2013; Olajuyigbe & Fasakin, 2010; Omonona & Fajimi, 2011; Osundare et al., 2020; Nadabo, & Dakyong, 2023;). The majority of these studies report positive household willingness to pay for improved water supply services. Their findings have informed decisions on infrastructure expansion, tariff design, and the targeting of water subsidies.

In Northern Nigeria, empirical evidence on households' WTP for improved public water supply is expanding (Ahmad, 2017; Ajamu et al., 2022; Aminu & Nyor, 2021; Ayanshola et al., 2013; Bichi, 2013; Dauda et al., 2014; Sheka et al., 2020; Yacob et al., 2013). However, studies specific to Katsina State have largely focused on water supply deficits, seasonal water quality variations, and household coping strategies, with limited attention to estimating the monetary value households attach to safe and reliable public water services (Inkani & Mashi, 2016; Sadauki et al., 2022; Sani & Scholz, 2021, 2022; Yusuf & Nuraddeen, 2020). The Katsina State Government has recently expressed commitment to expanding the capacity and coverage of the Katsina State Water Board (KTSWB) through the Zobe Dam Water Distribution Phase II Project (Surajo, 2021). The project targets improved access to safe water services in Batagarawa, Charanchi, Dutsinma, Kankia, and Kurfi towns. Furthermore, the state is a beneficiary of a ₦20 billion World Bank-supported Sustainable Urban and Rural Water Supply, Sanitation and Hygiene (SURWASH) programme aimed at upgrading and scaling up public water supply and sanitation infrastructure (Michael, 2024; Nadabo, 2023). Ensuring the financial sustainability of these investments requires an understanding of beneficiaries' willingness to contribute to operation and maintenance costs.

Against this backdrop, this study examines semi-urban households' willingness to pay for improved public water services in Katsina State. The findings reveal substantial latent demand for improved public water services with a mean monthly WTP of ₦6,567.88 (US\$4.10), approximately 62% higher than the prevailing tariff. The evidence might support optimal tariff setting that aligns with on-going infrastructure expansion and cost-recovery strategies. The remainder of the paper is organised as follows: Section 2 reviews the literature; Section 3 presents the theoretical framework; Section 4 outlines the methodology; Section 5 discusses the results; and Section 6 concludes with policy recommendations.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Despite persistent poverty and inequality in many developing countries, a substantial body of empirical literature documents households' willingness to pay (WTP) for improved public water services. Evidence from Sub-Saharan Africa and Asia consistently suggests that households are willing to contribute financially to improvements in water quality, reliability, and accessibility.

For instance, Getinet *et al.*, (2024) used a seemingly unrelated bivariate probit regression to analysed data from 272 households in Ethiopia's Central Rift Valley. The authors found that 70.96% of respondents were willing to pay up to 7.4% of their annual income for improved potable water supply. Socioeconomic characteristics such as income (farm and off-farm), gender, time spent fetching water, and current water expenditure positively influenced WTP, while larger household size, higher bid levels, and satisfaction with existing water services reduced WTP. Similarly, Islam *et al.*, (2022) employed multivariate probit and single-bounded contingent valuation models to examines data collected in Khulna, Bangladesh. The authors reported an average WTP of US\$5.05 per month for improved services. Also, education, income, and water collection time emerged as significant determinants. Comparable findings are reported by Eridadi *et al.* (2021) in Ethiopia, Zvobgo (2021) in Zimbabwe, and Odwori (2020) in Kenya, where income, education, gender, access conditions, and water-related health risks consistently influenced households' WTP decisions. While reported WTP levels vary across contexts, the determinants appear remarkably stable: income, education, household size, water access conditions, and perceived service quality are recurrent explanatory factors.

In Nigeria, early contributions (e.g., Whittington *et al.*, 1991; Sule & Okeola, 2010; Olajuyigbe & Fasakin, 2010; Omonona & Fajimi, 2011; Ayanshola *et al.*, 2013; Bichi, 2013; Coster & Otufale, 2014; Dauda *et al.*, 2014; Dare, 2014; Kanayo *et al.*, 2013; Adenike & Titus, 2009; Yacob *et al.*, 2013) established positive household WTP for improved water services across various states. The literature has continued to expand in response to persistent deficits in water infrastructure nationwide. Recent studies reinforce earlier findings. Itoro (2024) analysed data collected from Akwa Ibom State using a Heckman two-step model. The result reveals that water quality, income, family size, and efficiency of water use significantly influenced WTP. Moreover, Ajamu *et al.* (2022) examining water pricing policy in Borno State using probit regression. The authors reported that although the existing flat tariff (₦300/month) was relatively low, households exhibited positive WTP. Similarly, Aminu and Nyor (2021) reported that 82.5% of rural households in Benue State were willing to pay ₦21.68 per 25 litres, with income, education, household size, and distance to water source as key determinants.

Evidence from Kano (Sheka *et al.*, 2020; Ahmad, 2017) highlights the high reliance on water vendors and significant price differentials between vendor-supplied water and public utility tariffs. Sheka *et al.* (2020) found that 90% of surveyed households expressed WTP for improved private water supply, with mean WTP of ₦1,119.51 per month. Ahmad (2017) similarly documented that households paid substantially higher prices to vendors compared to public utility tariffs and were willing to pay for in-house connections.

In Southern Nigeria, studies such as Akeju *et al.* (2018), Osundare *et al.* (2020), and Coster and Otufale (2016) consistently report WTP rates above 70%, with determinants including income, education, service reliability, water quality, household size, and connection costs. These studies provide robust evidence that Nigerian households generally value improvements in public water supply and are willing to contribute financially under appropriate tariff structures. The foregoing review indicated concentration of studies on WTP for improved water supply in Southern Nigeria. However, households' socioeconomic status varies across Nigerian regions.

For instance, Abubakar (2019) reporting that 78% of all households that use unprotected wells are domiciled in Northern Nigeria. Therefore, this study contributes to the growing WTP for improved water supply literature in Northern Nigeria.

3. METHODOLOGY AND DATA

Background of the Study Area

Katsina State is located in the North-West geopolitical zone of Nigeria, between latitudes 11°08'N and 13°22'N and longitudes 6°52'E and 9°20'E, covering approximately 23,938 square kilometres. The state comprises 34 Local Government Areas (LGAs). As of 2022, the projected population was estimated at 10,368,483 (National Population Commission [NPC], 2020). The population is predominantly Hausa-Fulani, with major economic activities including crop farming, livestock rearing, petty trading, and public sector employment. Water governance in the state is coordinated by the Katsina State Ministry of Water Resources, which oversees water supply, sanitation policy implementation, and conservation initiatives. The Ministry supervises three key agencies: the Katsina State Water Board (KTSWB), the Rural Water Supply and Sanitation Agency (RUWASSA), and the Small Towns Water Supply and Sanitation Agency (STOWA).

The Katsina State Water Board is statutorily mandated to provide potable water at affordable cost to urban and semi-urban areas. It operates water supply schemes across eight towns: Daura, Dutsi, Dutsinma, Funtua, Jibia, Malumfashi, Mashi, and Katsina with 12 functional schemes and a total installed treatment capacity of 179,035 m³/day. However, actual output remains below design capacity (KTSWB, 2023). Current domestic tariffs vary by connection type: Single tap connection is charge ₦1,650/month; internal plumbing: ₦4,800/month and internal plumbing with garden: ₦5,700/month. Thus, the average domestic tariff is approximately ₦4,050 per month (₦135 per day) (KTSWB, 2025). While the tariff structure reflects the Board's commitment to affordability, cost recovery remains a critical concern. The Zobe Dam Phase II Water Distribution Project aims to expand water distribution infrastructure to Batagarawa, Charanchi, Dutsinma, Kankia, and Kurfi LGAs. The Dam is located approximately 65 km south of Katsina metropolis (12°22'N, 7°30'E). Phase I already supplies Katsina town through Dutsinma, Kurfi, and Batagarawa. The Phase II expansion is expected to significantly improve service reliability and coverage in semi-urban communities.

3.1 Theoretical Framework

This study is grounded in consumer choice theory, which provides the analytical foundation for valuing non-market environmental goods such as improved public water services. Within this framework, households are assumed to maximise utility subject to income constraints, choosing between improved water services and alternative consumption bundles. The maximum amount a household is willing to pay for an improvement reflects the compensating variation associated with the proposed change in service quality. To operationalise this framework, the study employs the Contingent Valuation Method (CVM), a stated-preference approach widely used to estimate the economic value of non-market goods. The methodological foundations of CVM trace back to Ciriacy-Wantrup (1947) and Davis (1963), with subsequent theoretical and empirical refinements by Mitchell and Carson (1989), Hanemann (1994), and Portney (1994). CVM elicits individuals' willingness to pay by presenting respondents with a hypothetical but realistic improvement scenario and asking them to state the maximum amount they would pay for the proposed change. Following Whitehead and Haab (2013), this study adopts a mixed elicitation format combining dichotomous choice questions with iterative bidding and threshold values. This approach enhances statistical

efficiency while mitigating starting-point bias and strategic responses. Formally, let household utility be represented as:

$$U = U(Q, X, Z) \tag{1}$$

Where Q denotes water service quality (reliability, safety, and accessibility), X represents composite consumption of other goods, and Z captures household socioeconomic characteristics. An improvement in Q increases utility, and WTP represents the maximum reduction in X (income) the household is willing to accept while maintaining initial utility levels. Accordingly, households' stated WTP is modelled as a function of observable socioeconomic characteristics and service-related factors:

$$WTP_i = f(Y_i, H_i, S_i, P_i, \epsilon_i) \tag{2}$$

Where Y denotes income, H household characteristics (e.g., size, education), S service attributes (e.g., reliability, distance), P perceived quality indicators, and ϵ an error term. This framework allows empirical examination of how socioeconomic and service-related variables influence households' valuation of improved public water supply in Katsina State.

3.2 Research Design, Study Population and Sample Size

The study adopted a cross-sectional survey design within a case-study framework. The target population comprised households residing in the five LGAs expected to benefit from the Zobe Dam Phase II distribution project. The household population figure is obtained from the Katsina State Bureau of Statistics (KTSBS, 2025). A multistage sampling approach was employed as follows: Stage one is the Purposive selection of the five benefiting LGAs based on project relevance. Stage two involves random selection of streets using a lottery method (10 each in Batagarawa and Dutsinma; 5 each in Charanchi, Kankia, and Kurfi). And finally, stage three employed systematic sampling (skip interval of one household) living within the selected streets to arrive at the final respondents. Furthermore, the sample size was determined base on Yamane (1967) formula with 95% confidence level in equation (3). Also, Proportionate allocation formula in equation (4) was then used to determine sample sizes per town. Finally, Table 1 provides a summary of the study population and sample size for each LGAs.

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2} \tag{3}$$

Where: n= sample size, N= population, e= level of significance (0.05)

$$\begin{aligned} n &= \frac{215,237}{1 + 215,237(0.05)^2} \\ &= 399.3 \approx 400 \\ n_i &= \frac{N_i}{N} * n \tag{4} \end{aligned}$$

Where: n_i = sample size for town i: i=1,2.....5, N_i = Households figure for town i: i=1,2.....5

Table1. Distribution of Sample Size

Towns	Population	Sample Size
Batagarawa	50,088	93
Charanchi	40,234	75
Dutsin-ma	55,971	104
Kankia	42,457	79
Kurfi	26,487	49
Total	215,237	400

Source: Authors' Summary (2025)

3.3 Instrument of Data Collection

Primary data were collected using a structured questionnaire designed in accordance with Contingent Valuation Method (CVM) guidelines. The instrument comprised three sections: socioeconomic characteristics, perceptions of existing water supply services and contingent valuation scenario. To minimise information and strategic bias: A clear hypothetical market scenario was presented (improved safe, reliable water supply conditional on monthly payments above the current average tariff). A single-bounded dichotomous choice question was first administered (Yes/No to a specified bid). This was followed by an iterative bidding format to elicit maximum WTP. A follow-up certainty question was included to reduce hypothetical bias. The questionnaire was validated by the Research Department of KTSBS. Similarly, ethical clearance for the study was obtained from the bureau. Informed consent was obtained from all respondents at the initiation of the interview. Data were collected using KoBoToolbox digital platform on 13th –20th June 2025. Five trained enumerators (one per town) conducted the interviews using smartphones. A pilot survey was undertaken prior to the main survey to refine question wording, test the CVM scenario, and assess interview duration. Field supervision was maintained throughout to ensure data quality and adherence to protocol.

3.5 Techniques of Data Analysis

Data analysis was conducted using descriptive statistics (frequencies, means, standard deviations, charts) and econometric modelling. Given that WTP values are non-negative and may be censored at zero (for households unwilling to pay), a Tobit regression model was employed. The Tobit model is appropriate when the dependent variable is continuous but left-censored. Base on insight from Islam *et al.*, (2022) and Lopez-Feldman (2012) households stated preferences can be model as follows:

$$WTP_i = \gamma_0 + \gamma_1 Y_i + \gamma_2 H_i + \gamma_3 G_i + \gamma_4 A_i + \gamma_5 E_i + \gamma_6 C_i + \gamma_7 Q_i + \omega_i \quad (5)$$

Where i represent the i th number of individuals; WTP_i represents the amount household are willingness to pay for improved public water supply; Y_i = household income, H_i = household size, G_i = household head gender, A_i =age of households head, E_i = education level of household head, C_i = cost of alternative water sources, Q_i = perceived water quality by household; ω_i is the error term and γ is a vector of the parameters that need to be estimated. The model enables examination of the socioeconomic and service-related determinants of households' stated WTP for improved public water supply.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS OF FINDINGS

4.1 Summary of Respondents’ Socioeconomic Background

Table 2 summarises the socioeconomic characteristics of the 400 sampled households across the five towns. The mean monthly household income was ₦135,668 (approximately US\$85), with a relatively high standard deviation (₦89,648), indicating substantial income dispersion across households. On a per capita basis, this corresponds to approximately US\$10.6 per person per day for a typical household of eight members; above the international extreme poverty threshold. However, the wide variation in income suggests heterogeneity in households’ capacity to pay for improved services. The average household size was 7.5 members, while the mean age of household heads was 44.5 years, indicating a predominantly middle-aged population. Male-headed households constituted 85.5% of the sample.

In terms of education, nearly half of respondents possessed post-secondary qualifications (40.25% tertiary; 3% postgraduate), suggesting relatively high literacy levels compared to rural northern contexts. Housing characteristics show that 50.5% lived in semi-detached houses, while 49.75% used ventilated pit latrines. These characteristics are important for interpreting WTP outcomes. Larger households may exhibit higher demand for reliable water due to greater consumption needs. Higher income and education levels are theoretically associated with greater awareness of health risks and stronger preferences for improved service quality. Conversely, sanitation type may influence water demand intensity (e.g., water-closet systems typically require greater water reliability than pit latrines).

Table 2. Respondents’ Socio-economic Background

Variables	n (%)	Mean	Sd	Min	Max
HHsize	400	7.507	5.078825	1	26
Age	400	44.5	11.43095	20	75
Income	400	135667.5	89647.89	12000	600000
	n(%)			n(%)	
Gender	400	Housing			
Male	342 (85.5%)	Traditional Mud		114 (28.5%)	
Female	58 (14.5%)	Structure		202 (50.5%)	
Education	400	Semi-detached house		80 (20%)	
Islamiyya	82 (20.5)	Bungalow/duplex		3 (0.75%)	
Primary	17 (4.25%)	Rooms/let in house		1 (0.25%)	
Secondary	102 (25.5)	Other		398	
Tertiary	161 (40.25%)	Toilet		103(25.88)	
Postgraduate	12 (3%)	Pit Latrine (no		198(49.75)	
Vocational	26 (6.5)	ventilation)		61(15.33%)	
		Ventilated Pit Latrine		36(9.05%)	
		Water Closet			
		Public toilet			

Sources: Field Survey (2025)

4.2 Water Supply Situation in the Study Area

Base on figure 1, approximately 47% of respondents reported no access to any public water source (piped connection, borehole, or public well), indicating a significant infrastructure deficit. Shared public boreholes were the dominant public source, reflecting the intervention role of RUWASSA in expanding access through borehole provision. Access to piped connections was limited and largely confined to parts of Dutsinma where coverage by the

Katsina State Water Board exists. However, even connected households reported intermittent supply. Furthermore, Figure 2 reveals that 59% of households rely on private water vendors to meet daily water needs. This aligns with earlier evidence from Northern Nigeria (e.g., Ahmad, 2017; Sheka et al., 2020; Whittington et al., 1991) highlighting the critical role of informal vendors in filling public supply gaps. Additionally, 13.7% use private wells, 12.5% use private boreholes. Also, Smaller proportions rely on storage, rivers/streams, or neighbours

Figure 1. Use and Availability of Public Water Sources
 Source: Authors’ Estimation based on Field Survey Data (2025)

Figure 2. Alternative Water Sources Used by the Respondents
 Source: Authors’ Estimation based on Field Survey Data (2025)

Table 3 indicated that Seventy-four per cent of respondents expressed concern about water safety, while 85% reported concerns about reliability. Among households purchasing from vendors, substantial proportion questioned water quality. This attested to the documented evidence that private water vendors paid more attention to the distance of the water source rather than its quality (Ahmad, 2017). Perceived unreliability was especially high for rainwater storage and stored water systems. These findings reinforce the hypothesis that dissatisfaction with existing water quality and reliability increases demand for improved public supply.

Table 3: Quality and Reliability of the water from Alternative Source sources

Water source	Quality		Reliability	
	Not Safe	Safe	Non-reliable	Reliable
All	296 (74%)	104 (26%)	341 (85%)	59 (15%)
Buying from vendor	160	76	206	30
From Neighbor	5	2	5	2
Private Borehole	40	10	41	9
Private Well	50	5	42	13
Rainwater Storage	2	2	4	0
River/Stream/Dam	11	8	15	4
Water Storage	28	1	28	1
	400 (100%)		400 (100%)	

Source: Field Survey (2025)

4.3 Respondents’ Willingness to Pay for Improve Public Water Supply

Figure 3 shows that a striking 88% of respondents were willing to pay above the current average domestic tariff (₦4,050 per month). Only 4% were unwilling to pay anything. The high positive WTP rate signals strong latent demand for improved service provision and suggests substantial scope for cost recovery. A small proportion of respondents 8% express their WTP below the current average tariff

Figure 3. Maximum Willingness to Pay For Improved Public Water Supply

Source: Authors’ Estimation based on Field Survey Data (2025)

Furthermore, Table 4 reports that the mean monthly WTP was ₦6,567.88 (US\$4.10), approximately 62% higher than the current average tariff. This represents about 4.8% of mean household income as well as 5.5% of median household income. These ratios indicate that improved public water supply is perceived as a valuable household expenditure, though affordability considerations remain relevant for lower-income groups. Similarly, the average WTP amount for each of the local towns was above the current KTSWB average monthly domestic tariff: Batagarawa ₦5,744.086 (\$3.59), Charanchi ₦5,575.333 (\$3.48), Dutsinma ₦5,971.154 (\$3.73), Kankia ₦8883.544(\$5.55), Kurfi ₦7346.939 (\$4.59). The minimum value of zero is consistent with the earlier finding that 4% of respondents are not willing to pay. When compared with previous reported WTP values in USA\$ our result is higher than that of Sheka *et al.*, (2020)-\$3.11 and lower than that of Akeju *et al.*, (2018), \$4.5 and Coster *et al.*, (2016)-\$14.4. These findings positions Katsina’s semi-urban WTP within the mid-range of national estimates.

Table 4. Average willingness to Pay

Average Willingness To Pay (WTP)					
		WTP		Monthly household Income	
Obs	400	Percentiles (₦)		Percentiles	(₦)
Mean (₦)	6567.875	50%	7,000	50%	120,000
Std dev(₦)	2783.67	75%	8,000	75%	165,000
Skewness	-	90%	10,000	90%	250,000
	0.4156372				
Kurtosis	3.750082	95%	10,000	95%	335,000
Min	0	99%	13,500	99%	450,000
Max	₦15,000				

Groups				
	Mean (₦)	Std (₦)	Min (₦)	Max (₦)
Batagarawa	5744.086	3603.334	0	10500
Charanchi	5575.333	2610.612	0	15000
Dutsinma	5971.154	1290.042	4000	10000
Kankia	8883.544	1864.543	800	15000
Kurfi	7346.939	2594.473	0	15000

Source: Authors’ Estimation based on Field Survey Data (2025)

Figure 4. Respondents’ Valuation of Water attributes

Source: Authors’ estimates based on Field Survey Data, (2025)

Furthermore, figure 4 depicts water attributes that households in the study area valued the most. It appears that health benefits was the most value attributes as 82% of respondents reported to have put highest premium on health benefit that will accompanied in-house connection as a result of improved public water supply. This is consistent with safety concern acknowledge by household who relied on private water vendors to meet their daily water demand. Aside this, convenience follows with 76% of households valuing convenience that in-house connection might bring. Additionally, water quality follows with 60% and reliability with 54%.

4.4 Factors Affecting Respondents’ WTP for Improved Public Water Supply

Table 5 reported the Tobit regression results; it is evident that income, age, education and cost of water from alternative source are significant determinants of the Willingness to pay (WTP) for improved water supply while household size and gender are not. For example, a ₦1,000

increase in respondent monthly income is associated with a ₦5 increase in WTP amount. This agrees with the earlier findings that income play a vital role in households' decision to pay for improved water supply (Akeju et al., 2018; Aminu & Nyor, 2021; Eridadi et al., 2021; Itoro, 2024; Sheka et al., 2020; Twerefou et al., 2015). This result implies that improved water supply is viewed as a necessity rather than a luxury good.

Table 5. Tobit Regression Results

Dependent variable: WTP			
Variable	Coefficient	Standard error	t-statistic
Income	0.005***	0.0018	2.78
Household size	7.012	34.08	0.21
Gender	380.4	413.3	0.92
Age	44.34***	14.93	2.97
Education	503.7***	85.53	5.89
Cost	0.382***	0.1376	2.77
Quality	1291***	285.3	4.53
Constant	-928.3	1017	-0.91
No of Observation	400	LR ch2(7)	91.43
Uncensored	383	Prob>Chi2	0.0000
Left-censored	17	Pseudo R2	0.0126
Right-censored	0		

Source: Authors' Estimation based on Field Survey Data, (2025)

Additionally, older household head were more willing to pay for improved public water supply. As household head grow older by a year, he is more likely to pay additional ₦ 44.34 for improved public water supply (Eridadi et al., 2021; Singh, 2020). This implies older households heads tend to value more, the convenience and reliability that might accompany improved public water supply service compare to a middle age households head due to reduced tolerance for water-fetching burdens. Furthermore, an additional year of schooling is associated with a ₦503.7 increase in households head WTP amount. This is in line with earlier results reported by (Adeoti, 2011; Akeju et al., 2018; Aminu & Nyor, 2021; Coster & Otufale, 2016; Rahman et al., 2017; Sarker & Alam, 2013). This suggests that awareness and information play a key role in valuation of improved water services.

Similarly, a ₦1,000 increase in the cost of alternative water sources is link with ₦382 increases in WTP amount. This is consistent with the result of earlier studies by (Getinet et al., 2024; Kidu & Ewnetu, 2015; Mezgebo & Ewnetu, 2015; Sheka et al., 2020). This result confirms substitution effects; households facing high vendor prices are more inclined to support improved public supply. Likewise, the coefficient for water quality is also statistically significant, indicating that respondents who perceive their water as unsafe are willing to pay ₦1,291 more for improved water supply compared to those who perceive their water as safe. This is in tandem with the findings of (Akeju et al., 2018; Aminu & Nyor, 2021; Ayanshola et al., 2013; Getinet et al., 2024; Abdullahi, et al., 2019; Itoro, 2024; Yakubu, et al., 2019; Wendimu & Bekele, 2011). This points to the importance of health-risk perception in demand formation. The insignificant effect of household size on WTP for improved public water supply contradict the finding of (Akeju et al., 2018; Itoro, 2024; Kebede & Tariku, 2016). This reflects labour pooling effects in large households, reducing the perceived opportunity cost of water collection. Likewise, household head gender does not significantly affect WTP in the studied area. This finding is contrary with the argument that females household members bear much burden of collecting water and are likely to support in-house pipe connection from an improved

public water supply service (Entele & Lee, 2019; Abdullahi, & Nadabo, 2025; Getinet et al., 2024). This suggests that water decision-making may be economically rather than demographically driven in this context.

5 CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study provides empirical evidence on households' willingness to pay for improved public water supply in semi-urban Katsina State. The study data was collected from 400 households. Descriptive statistics and Tobit regression were used for analysis. The Key findings show that: 47% lack access to public water infrastructure, 59% rely on private vendors, 88% are willing to pay above the current tariff. Furthermore, mean WTP was about ₦6,567.88 (\$4.10) per month. Also, income, education, age, alternative water cost, and perceived water quality are significant determinants of households WTP. The results indicate strong effective demand for improved water services and demonstrate households' readiness to contribute to cost recovery. In terms of recommendation, the high WTP justifies accelerated implementation of the Zobe Dam Phase II project to expand reliable supply. Also, given that mean WTP exceeds current tariffs; there is scope for revising tariff structures to enhance financial sustainability while maintaining affordability safeguards. Again, income heterogeneity suggests the need for tiered pricing or lifeline tariffs to protect low-income households. Additionally, the strong education effect implies that awareness programmes about water safety and health risks could further enhance public support for improved supply. Future studies should extend coverage to rural and fully urban areas to enable state-wide policy design and examine dynamic demand responses once improved services are operational.

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